

Management of Dental Anxiety and Fear

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Abstract

Dental pain, anxiety and fear are important factors that prevent patients from seeking dental care. Dental anxiety is a prevalent issue which every dental practitioner will face. As dental anxiety involves personal consequences for the affected patients - as well as hampering the clinical performance of the dental profession – this matter should be taken seriously and dealt with accordingly. The treatment of dental anxiety thus should be within the competence of the general practitioner in this research we will clarify the measures a general dentist can take to understand what is happening with these patients and how to ease the dental treatment of fearful patients. Studies indicate that memory of dental pain is “reconstructed” over time. They found that highly anxious patients tended to overestimate the pain they would feel prior to the dental procedure and also overestimate the pain experienced, when asked to recall it later. This pattern of findings has also been seen in other studies. In a study which examined 60 dental patients who twice underwent oral surgery, the highly anxious patients expected more pain than they actually experienced during the procedure, and also required more time for management than did patients with low anxiety levels.

Keywords: anxiety, fear, dental phobia, management, communication

1. Introduction

Over the past years, clinical practice of dentistry has benefited from advances in materials, techniques infection control and also technologies. However, dental anxiety is still a common problem many patients worldwide suffer from it and it remains a significant challenge in providing dental care. Whereas Anxiety is an emotional state that helps normal individuals to defend themselves against a variety of threats; anxiety disorders are a dysregulation of these normal defensive mechanisms, with either excessive or deficient in emotional responses (Abrahamsson KH et. al. 2003).

2. Prevalence

It was estimated that as many as 74.3% of patients experi-

ence some degree of dental fear, from mild to severe (Milgrom P. et. al. 1995). Approximately 5 to 10 percent of adults are considered to experience the dental phobia; that is, they are so fearful of receiving dental treatment that they avoid dental care at all costs Many dentally fearful people will only seek dental care when they have a dental emergency, such as a toothache or dental abscess (Gatchel RJ et. al. 1983).

3. The difference between anxiety, fear and phobia

A distinction has been made between dental anxiety, dental fear, and dental phobia.

- DENTAL ANXIETY is a reaction to an unknown danger. Anxiety is extremely common, and most

people experience some degree of dental anxiety especially if they're about to have something done which they've never experienced before. Basically, it's a fear of the unknown.

- **DENTAL FEAR** is a reaction to a known danger ("I know what the dentist is going to do, been there, done that – I'm scared"), which involves a fight-or-flight response when confronted with the threatening stimulus.
- **DENTAL PHOBIA** is basically the same as fear, only much stronger ("I know what happens when I go to the dentist – there's no way I'm going back if I can help it. I'm so terrified I feel sick"). The fight-or-flight response occurs when just thinking about or being reminded of the threatening situation. Someone with a dental phobia will *avoid* dental care at all costs until either a physical problem or the psychological burden of the phobia becomes overwhelming (Moore R et al. 1993).

4. Measuring dental anxiety

Here are various instruments for researchers which attempt to measure the degree of the fear, such as Corah's Dental Anxiety Scale (DAS) and a shorter version, the Modified Dental Anxiety Scale (MDAS) (Locker D. et. al. 1991).

5. Causes of dental anxiety and fear

- *Bad experiences:* Dental phobia is most often caused by bad or in some cases horrific experiences at a dentist's (studies suggest that this is true for about 80 -85% of dental phobias, but there are difficulties with obtaining representative samples). This not only includes painful dental visits, but also psychological behaviours such as being humiliated by a dentist.
- *A history of abuse:* Dental phobia is also common in people who have been sexually abused. A history of bullying or having been physically or emotionally abused by a person in authority may also contribute to developing dental phobia, especially in combination with bad experiences with dentists.
- *Uncaring dentist:* It is often thought, even among dental professionals, that it is the fear of pain that keeps people from seeing a dentist. But even where the pain is the person's major concern, it is not pain per se that is necessarily the problem. Otherwise, dental phobics would not avoid the dentist even when in pain from the toothache. Rather, it is pain inflicted by a dentist who is perceived as cold and controlling that has a huge psychological impact. Pain caused by a dentist who is perceived as caring is much less likely to result in psychological trauma (Weiner et al, 1999).
- *Humiliation:* Other causes of dental phobia include insensitive, humiliating remarks by a dentist or hygienist. In fact, insensitive remarks and the intense feelings of humiliation they provoke are one of the main factors which can cause or contribute to a dental phobia. Human beings are social animals, and negative social evaluation will upset most people, apart from the most thick-skinned individuals. If you're the sensitive type, negative evaluation can be shattering.
- *Vicarious learning:* Another cause of dental anxiety is observational learning. This appears to be of only minor importance, judging by our forum and by the available research (e.g. Townend, Dimigen and Diane, 1999). If a parent or another caregiver is afraid of dentists, children may pick up on this and learn to be afraid as well, even in the absence of bad experiences. Hearing other people's horror stories about visits to the psychodentist can have a similar effect. Also, the depiction of "the dentist" in the media (especially children's films/cartoons and comedies, and of course horror movies) can cause people to develop dental fears. Examples include "Horton Hears a who" and "Nick at Night".
- *Preparedness:* People may be inherently "prepared" to learn certain phobias, such as needle phobia. For millions of years people who quickly learned to avoid snakes, heights, and lightning (and sharp objects, such as needles, which would not have been sterilized in those days, apart from giving you a nasty sting!) probably had a good chance to survive and to transmit their genes. So it may not take a particularly painful encounter with a needle to develop a phobia.
- *Post-Traumatic Stress:* Research suggests that people who've had horrific dental experiences (unsurprisingly) suffer from symptoms typically reported by people with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). This is characterized by intrusive thoughts of the bad experience and nightmares

about dentists or dental situations (Economou GC. et al. 2003).

6. Management

Nearly two thirds of dentists believe that treating an anxious patient presents a challenge to them in everyday practice. Identifying these patients and putting appropriate measures in place is, therefore, essential. Patients displaying behaviours such as frequent cancellation, delaying or rescheduling appointments may be doing so because of dental fear and anxiety (Armfield JM. Et. al. 2006) Upon identification of an anxious or fearful patient, a range of measures can be put into place.

For example: allowing sufficient time for the dental appointment, Minimizing triggers, following the “4 S” principle described earlier, e.g. by altering the surgery set-up, the dental assistant can place instruments where they are blocked from view or covered⁸, or could spray a scented oil fragrance to reduce the clinical aroma of the treatment room, Introducing relaxation methods (see below), Provision of extra control during the procedure, Using distraction techniques, e.g. music via headphones, video glasses, and virtual reality glasses (especially for adults), Providing more efficient anaesthesia, or using adjunctive methods, e.g. peristaltic injectors (Wand™), topical creams (EMLA™), and transcutaneous nerve stimulation, Referral to cognitive or behavioural specialists or psychologists for anxiety management and behaviour therapy.

Conscious sedation use pharmacological agents. Using a multifaceted approach rather than relying on one single strategy improves the likelihood of success. The management of anxious patients will vary depending on factors such as the patients’ age, anticipated degree of cooperation, and their medical and/or dental history (Quteish DS. et al. 2001).

Dentist behavior targeted to anxiety reduction, such as having a calm manner, being friendly, giving moral support, being reassuring about pain, preventing pain, and working efficiently, have been shown to reduce anxiety (Corah NL et. al. 1988).

Communication

Staff-patient communication with patients plays a very

important role in anxiety reduction. Providing verbal support and reassurance is a frequently used strategy (Moore R et. al. 2001). To be maximally effective, this approach needs to be taken by all staff members with whom the patient interacts. A receptionist who notes anxious patients can schedule sufficient time for the appointment, allowing the clinical operators some additional time to carefully explain procedures, and then to proceeding slowly with treatment.

Relaxation therapies

Relaxation therapies can enhance trust and give patients the feeling of control over their psychological state. These methods can be very effective in motivated and cooperative patients, and can be used before and during a treatment appointment. These techniques are safe, have no side effects, and give patients more control over their anxiety level. A common method is Jacobsen’s progressive muscular relaxation, which relaxes patients by reducing physical (muscle) tension, and makes them more aware of their stressed and aroused state, and how to address this. Their greater feeling of control over the situation and over their anxiety symptoms should translate into greater ability in coping with the stress of dental treatment. A simple scheme for progressive muscular relaxation involves tensing and relaxing groups of muscles in turn, for example from the feet through the lower body and abdomen to the thorax and then the head and neck.

Another simple method for promoting relaxation is paced breathing, where patients inhale using deep diaphragmatic breathing, hold for 5 seconds, then exhale over 5 seconds. This slow paced breathing can be combined imagery-based methods with the use of particular words, visual images or thoughts that are linked with the breathing rhythm, for example using a cue word such as “CALM” on the exhalation cycle. With repeated practice, patients can move more quickly into the relaxed state¹¹. Relaxation and breathing techniques have been used successfully with patients who are fearful of receiving dental treatments, and can be easily taught to patients and applied quickly in a dental environment (Hainsworth JM et. al. 2005).

Distraction

Virtual reality techniques which involve the use of coloured glasses to experience a three-dimensional computer-generated images during dental treatment, have been shown to engage and relax adults, but less positive results

for children (Sullivan C. et. al. 2000). By using distraction and other anxiety reduction measures, with repeated positive experiences, a patient's level of anxiety should reduce. For example, Marks et al. have reported that prolonged exposure to nontraumatic anxiety cues helps patients adapt to these situations and will diminish their excessive responses (Gatchel RJ et. al. 1983).

Techniques with reduced annoyance factors

Restorative dentistry has, historically, a strong association with both pre-treatment dental anxiety and fear of pain during treatment. The term "annoyance factor" refers to the patient's subjective reaction to restorative dentistry procedures such as cavity preparation, and is a combination of the pressure applied to the tooth, the vibrations and noise recorded through the bones of the skull, the heat and smell generated at the interface between the tooth and the bur and the time taken to perform a given task (Nadin G. et al. 1997). New methods for restorative dentistry have reduced annoyance factors compared with conventional rotary instruments, and in so doing they help to eliminate or reduce a major trigger of dental anxiety.

Atraumatic restorative technique (ART), air abrasion, chemo-mechanical caries removal (Carisolv™), and middle infrared lasers may now be considered alternative methods for tooth preparation and caries removal. The erbium (Er: YAG and Er, Cr: YSGG) lasers act selectively on water present in hard tissues, because of their wavelengths and are able to ablate carious enamel and dentine. When used properly they may induce a depressed state of responsiveness in pulpal nociceptors (Mount GJet. al. 2005). Generally, patients undergoing cavity preparation with erbium lasers do not need local anaesthesia. Large scale clinical trials report that only 2-5% of patients will request local anaesthesia although many patients experience slight, intermittent sensations of cold in their teeth, probably caused by the cooling effects of water evaporation during laser pulses (Hainsworth JM et al. 2005). Suppressive effects on nerve firing give an analgesic effect with the duration of 10-15 minutes. Use of this analgesic effect can maintain comfort in anxious patients, allowing treatment of several teeth, in one appointment, without the need for injected local anaesthesia.

The ART method has been used extensively in dentistry for

conservative management of open cavitations in dentine. On the other hand, chemo-mechanical caries removal is a minimally invasive method, which involves the selective removal of soft carious dentine without the painful removal of sound dentine during cavity preparation, as a form of chemically accelerated ART. Use of these novel methods may be effectively targeted to anxious dental patients, where the different methods reduce the major stimuli for anxiety and also provide a distraction effect, thus giving overall a reduction in dental anxiety (Eitner S. et. al. 2006).. If patients are aware of these methods, they may petition the dentist to use them for future dental treatment. A study by Eitner et al. found that 60% of the participants expected to be treated better if they described themselves as very anxious to the dentist (Eitner S. et al. 2006).

Sedation

Conscious sedation techniques have been proven to be reliable and safe for managing dental anxiety (Nadin G & Coulthard P. 1997) while more severely anxious and uncooperative patients can be treated under general anaesthesia. Agents such as nitrous oxide and oxygen administered by inhalation are in common use, however for anxiolytic agents, a wide range of routes of administration exist, including ingestion, rectal suppository, intramuscular injection, and intravenous injection for direct application into the circulation, as in the case of midazolam, diazepam and other benzodiazepines (Coulthard P. et. al. 1997). Agents used for sedation must produce a relaxed state rapidly for the period needed, but must then wear off rapidly so that the patient can return to their normal state.

7. Conclusion

Dental anxiety is a serious and very common problem in dental practice. One in five adults suffering from dental anxiety or phobia, Sex and age appear to be important factors linked to dental anxiety, with middle age females being particularly common within the dentally anxious group. Dental anxiety is a complex phenomenon, which is influenced by personality, fear of pain, past traumatic dental experiences in childhood, and dentally anxious family members or relatives or friends, the management of the dentally anxious patients should involve considering both complementary and pharmacological means. Helping highly anxious patients to overcome their fear of dental treatment is

a challenge, but achieving it will have great effect on oral health and the patient health in general.

8. References

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